

Table S1: Genera in families and subfamilial lineages within *Gobioidei*. Lineage names follow Agorreta et al. (2013). Lineage membership is as delineated by Thacker & Hardman (2005), Thacker & Roje (2011), Thacker (2013, 2015), adjusted in accordance with the results of McCraney et al. (2025), and including all genera described as of May 2025. *Gobioidei* contains nine families, 327 genera, and 2,435 species.

Family/Lineage	Genera
RHYACICHTHYIDAE	<i>Protogobius, Rhyacichthys</i>
ODONTOBUTIDAE	<i>Maipotera, Microdous, Micropercops, Neodontobutis, Odontobutis, Percottus, Sineleotris, Terateleotris</i>
MILYERINGIDAE	<i>Milyeringa, Typhleotris</i>
ELEOTRIDAE	<i>Allomogurnda, Belobranchus, Bunaka, Caecieleotris, Calumia, Dormitator, Eleotris, Formorsaneleotris, Giurus, Gobiomorphus, Gobiomorus, Hemieleotris, Hypseleotris, Leptophilypnion, Leptophilypnus, Microphilypnus, Mogurnda, Guavina, Philypnodon, Ratsirakia, Tateurndina</i>
XENISTHMIDAE	<i>Allomicrodesmus, Gymnoxenisthmus, Paraxenisthmus, Rotuma, Tyson, Xenisthmus</i>
BUTIDAE	<i>Bostrychus, Butis, Incara, Kribia, Odonteleotris, Ophiocara, Oxyeleotris, Paloa, Parviparma, Pogoneleotris, Prionobutis</i>
THALASSELEOTRIDIDAE	<i>Grahamichthys, Tempestichthys, Thalasseleotris</i>

OXUDERCIDAE

- Acanthogobius* *Acanthogobius, Amblychaeturichthys, Astrabe, Chaenogobius, Chaeturichthys, Clariger, Clevelandia, Eucyclogobius, Eutaeniichthys, Evermannia, Gillichthys, Gymnogobius, Ilogton, Ilypnus, Inu, Lepidogobius, Lethops, Leucopsarion, Lophiogobius, Luciogobius, Papuligobius, Polyspondylogobius, Pterogobius, Quietula, Rhinogobius, Sagamia, Suruga, Siphonogobius, Tomiyamia, Tridentiger, Typhlogobius*
- Mugilogobius* *Brachygobius, Caecogobius, Chlamydogobius, Eugnathogobius, Gobiopterus, Hemigobius, Mistichthys, Mugilogobius, Nesogobius, Paedogobius, Pandaka, Pseudogobiopsis, Pseudogobius, Redigobius, Stigmatogobius, Tamanka, Tasmanogobius, Wuhanlinigobius*
- Periophthalmus* *Amblyotrypauchen, Apocryptes, Apocryptodon, Biandongella, Boleophthalmus, Brachyamblyopus, Caragobius, Ctenotrypauchen, Gymnoamblyopus, Karsten, Odontamblyopus, Oxuderces, Parapocryptes, Paratrypauchen, Periophthalmodon, Periophthalmus, Pseudapocryptes, Pseudotrypauchen, Reptiliceps, Scartelaos, Sovvityazius, Taenioides, Trypauchen, Trypauchenichthys, Trypauchenopsis, Zappa*
- Pomatoschistus* *Buenia, Crystallogobius, Deltentosteus, Economidichthys, Hyrcanogobius, Knipowitschia, Lebetus, Ninnigobius, Orsinigobius, Pomatoschistus, Pseudaphya, Speleogobius*
- Stenogobius* *Akihito, Awaous, Awaouichthys, Cotylopus, Ctenogobius, Eoorthodus, Gnatholepis, Gobioides, Gobionellus, Lentipes, Oligolepis, Oxyurichthys, Parasicydium, Parawaous, Sicydium, Sicyopterus, Sicyopus, Smilosicyopus, Stenogobius, Stiphodon*

GOBIIDAE

<i>Aphia</i>	<i>Aphia, Lesueurigobius</i>
<i>Asterropteryx</i>	<i>Amblyeleotris, Asterropteryx, Ctenogobiops, Gladiogobius, Vanderhorstia</i>
<i>Callogobius</i>	<i>Barbuligobius, Callogobius, Mangarinus, Palutrus, Phoxacromion</i>
<i>Cryptocentrus</i>	<i>Cryptocentrus, Cryptocentroides, Discordipinna, Lotilia, Mahidolia, Myersina, Psilogobius, Stonogobiops, Tomiyamichthys</i>
<i>Glossogobius</i>	<i>Bathygobius, Dotsugobius, Glossogobius, Grallenia, Psammogobius</i>
<i>Gobiodon</i>	<i>Bryaninops, Eviota, Gobiodon, Kelloggella, Larsonella, Lobulogobius, Lubricogobius, Luposicya, Minysicya, Paragobiodon, Phyllogobius, Pleurosicya, Sueviota</i>
<i>Gobiopsis</i>	<i>Acentrogobius, Afurcagobius, Ancistrogobius, Arcygobius, Arenigobius, Aulopareia, Cabillus, Drombus, Echinogobius, Exyrias, Favonigobius, Gobiopsis, Hazeus, Heteroplopomus, Istigobius, Macrodontogobius, Oplopomus, Oplopomops, Paragobiopsis, Parachaeturichthys, Platygobiopsis, Porogobius, Silhouettea, Yongeichthys, Yoga</i>
<i>Gobiosoma</i>	<i>Aboma, Akko, Antilligobius, Aruma, Barbulifer, Birdsongichthys, Bollmannia, Carrigobius, Chriolepis, Cryptopsilotris, Elacatinus, Eleotrica, Evermannichthys, Ginsburgellus, Gobiosoma, Gobulus, Gymneleotris, Microgobius, Nes, Ophiogobius, Paedovaricus, Palatogobius, Parrella, Pariah, Pinnichthys, Psilotris, Risor, Robinsichthys, Tigrigobius, Varicus, Vomerogobius</i>
<i>Gobius</i>	<i>Anatirostrum, Babka, Benthophilus, Benthophiloides, Caffrogobius, Caspiosoma, Cerogobius, Chromogobius, Corcyrogobius, Coryogalops, Croilia, Didogobius, Ebomegobius, Gammogobius, Gobius, Gorogobius,</i>

	<i>Gymnesigobius, Heteroleotris, Marcelogobius, Mauligobius, Mesogobius, Millerigobius, Nematogobius, Neogobius, Odondebuenia, Padogobius, Pascua, Peter, Ponticola, Proterorhinus, Sufflogobius, Thorogobius, Vanneaugobius, Wheelerigobius, Zebrus</i>
<i>Gunnellichthys</i>	<i>Aioliops, Austrolethops, Cerdale, Clarkichthys, Gunnellichthys, Microdesmus, Navigobius, Nemateleotris, Oxymetopon, Paragunnellichthys, Parioglossus, Ptereleotris, Pterocerdale, Schindleria, Zagadkogobius</i>
<i>Kraemeria</i>	<i>Kraemeria, Gobitrichonotus, Parkraemeria, Schismatogobius</i>
<i>Lophogobius</i>	<i>Coryphopterus, Cristatogobius, Fusigobius, Lophogobius, Rhinogobiops</i>
<i>Priolepis</i>	<i>Egglestonichthys, Feia, Lythrypnus, Obliquogobius, Paratrimma, Priolepis, Trimma, Trimmatom, Tryssogobius</i>
<i>Valenciennea</i>	<i>Amblygobius, Koumansetta, Signigobius, Valenciennea</i>
